

Functional Hierarchical Search Results Data Analysis

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Abstract—¹NASA Ames, in collaboration with JSC ISS MOD, has been developing novel systems for searching across multiple heterogeneous data systems in order to facilitate rapid retrieval of relevant information for flight controllers on console and in their off-console duties.

Traditional data mining techniques to identify document similarity rely upon brute-force $O(n^2)$ cosine similarity of vectors representing text contained in the documents--an expensive and time-consuming operation that becomes unfeasible on large data sets such as those in use by the Shuttle and Station programs at NASA. This paper details a technique developed as part of this activity to identify documents similar to documents relevant and of interest to the user by leveraging the prior search results to produce a weighted graph of document relationships based upon search terms. This paper details the algorithms used, the user interface prototypes developed to evaluate the usefulness of similarity to the browsing activities of users, and the evaluation of the accuracy of this technique as compared with traditional data mining techniques

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1. INTRODUCTION

Search-Driven data analysis method proposed in this paper relies on search results produced by user specific queries, i.e. its user driven. Both naïve and sophisticated user demands for a simple search result that one can understand and should address the means of one's search. The systems available in the market perform data-analysis based on predefined classifications or ad-hock classification based on datasets; the results may or may not be relevant to users demand. The approach in this paper is a different perspective of data-analysis using not predefined rules of classifications but from user defined classification rules.

2. BACKGROUND

The more the data is structured the better the applications that can be built on top of it, with the advancement in XML databases, many such applications are addressing the needs of performing data-analysis at middle-tire level as a real-time data analyzer or a standalone application service. The approach in this paper depends on ²NETMARK extensible DataBase (XDB), a schema-less approach to save and index all kinds of textual data semi-structured, full-structured and un-structured. The advantage with NETMARK is it converts even the semi-structured data into a meaningful structured format, the sequence diagram in Figure-2.0 shows the process, NETMARK saves the meta-data associated with the document information as the context of the data. The search results produced by NETMARK are in well structured XML format. Some of the data-sets that ISS MOD search for are PVCS and Flight Controller procedure documents. PVCS documents are in well structured HTML format, the procedure documents are semi-structured documents in Word or PDF format.

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² A patent pending database technology from NASA Ames Research Center.

Figure-2.0

Traditional ³Text-Mining processes derive high-quality information by identifying patterns and trends, the bottom line is data-mining and text-mining extract previously unknown useful information, the process is unaware of what it is suppose to look for, as shown in Figure-2.1, the categorization is uncontrolled, the rules to define the categorization are not pre-defined, the rules are been formulated by the discovery of an unknown pattern runtime within the process. In case of clustering approach the rules are pre-defined at the design level. These data-analysis process produced results are very useful for pattern recognition problems in scientific environments but when it comes to a general user wishing to find related documents specific to ones search criteria this such process would be too expensive for the operation.

Figure-2.1

Most of the text-mining processes for document similarity analysis rely on numerical comparison functions like Cosine-Similarity function.

$$\text{Similarity}(D_i, D_j) = \text{Cos}(V(D_i), V(D_j))$$

Where D_i and D_j are two different documents and $V(D_i)$ and $V(D_j)$ are vectors associated with the documents. Such numerical process are computationally intense $O(n^2)$, particularly expensive when computing similarity on remote corpus unless corpus is cached. All the text is included in calculating the vectors in order to improve accuracy pre-processing techniques are been applied like Normalization (removal of stop words), establish semantic equivalence (taxonomies/ontology) etc.

This approach is suited for snapshot of data but if the data is changing dynamically the solution may not be applicable, as each updated document will require another $O(n^2)$ comparison, or at best an $O(n)$ per updated document, depending on the specific algorithm utilized. Traditional text-mining processes cannot address the following needs with respect to document-similarity, Cost-effective data-analysis for dynamically changing data. User-defined categorization rules for data-analysis.

3. APPROACH

The approach comprised of multiple phases, the first level can be mapped to traditional text-mining approaches, and will be explained in the analysis section of the document. The second phase depends on the first phase but performs data-analysis at a very granular level and so does the higher-levels.

The following Figure-3.0 gives a high-level picture of NETMARK client-server-services architecture, the focus of our approach is in the red-box section in the Figure-3.0. This approach can be used on any XML database as long as the search result sets produced by the database are structured result sets. Other then the first level data-analysis all other levels depend on the tag-elements in the XML data, the tags determine the context of the data. So in the result set XML hierarchy every level maps to a level for data-analysis, the more the levels, the granular the analysis is performed i.e. the more the data is structured the better the analysis results are. NETMARK is the best case for this approach because it keeps track of the contexts as well as the level associated with the context.

Both naive and sophisticated users provide search keywords to a search engine and that determines the search criteria. In the First-level the search criteria itself defines the categorization rule to do data-analysis on search results.

² _____
³ Wikipedia
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Text_mining

Figure-3.0

$${}^4F(S) \rightarrow \{ {}^6D_0, D_1, D_2, D_3, \dots \}$$

Where “S” is the search term and F(S) defines the search criteria that results to a finite set of documents that qualify the search criteria. Logically every document in the set is related to the other document in the same set. As the user keeps defining more search keywords the more result sets are produced.

$$F(T_0) \rightarrow {}^7R_0$$

$$F(T_1) \rightarrow R_1$$

$$F(T_2) \rightarrow R_2$$

...

Accumulating these sets of results, we have the set of result sets:

$${}^8S = \{ R_0, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n \}$$

Now let’s consider a smaller set “r”

$$r = \{ D_i, D_j \}$$

Where D_i and D_j are two different documents, there is a number of result sets wherein “r” is contained.

$$s \in S: \text{ where } r \subseteq R_n$$

The numbers of result sets determine the weight of relationship between document D_i and document D_j . In the specific example, if

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⁴ F : Denotes a Function

⁵ T : Denotes a Search String

⁶ D : Denotes a Result item, a Document

⁷ R : Denotes a set of Documents

⁸ S : Set of result sets

$$s = \{ R_1, R_7, R_6, R_5, R_3 \}$$

Then

$|s| = 5$, the cardinality of set “s” is the weighted relationship between D_i and D_j .

The more the user defines the search criteria, the stronger the relationship among similar document gets, such that the document relationships are directly proportional to number of search criteria that users define, the more the user uses the system the better the data-analysis results they find. This data-analysis technique results in an undirected weighted graph, with each node corresponding to a document and the edge determining the weight and relationship among documents as shown in Figure-3.1.

In the Second-phase NETMARK plays a vital role, the search function returns not only a document reference but a set of contexts wherein the search term has been found

So if

$$F(T) \rightarrow \{ D_0, D_1, D_2 \}$$

$$D_0 = \{ {}^9c_{00}, c_{01}, c_{02} \} \quad D_1 = \{ c_{01}, c_{04}, c_{05} \}$$

$$D_2 = \{ c_{04}, c_{02}, c_{05} \}$$

Where c_{ij} is the context at Level “i” and “j” is a unique identifier for each context at level “i”.

In other words

$$F(T) \rightarrow \{ \{ {}^9c_{00}, c_{01}, c_{02} \}, \{ c_{01}, c_{04}, c_{05} \}, \{ c_{04}, c_{02}, c_{05} \} \}$$

Let’s assume that the similarity of document D_i and D_j is 5 at first level i.e. no context involved. The Documents D_i and D_j may not be similar with weight 5 at second level.

As per our example

$$C_{D_0 D_1} = D_0 \cap D_1 = \{ c_{01} \}$$

$$| C_{D_0 D_1} | = 1$$

$$C_{D_0 D_2} = D_0 \cap D_2 = \{ c_{02} \}$$

$$| C_{D_0 D_2} | = 1$$

And

$$C_{D_1 D_2} = D_1 \cap D_2 = \{ c_{01}, c_{05} \}$$

$$| C_{D_1 D_2} | = 2$$

³ _____

⁹ c : Denotes a Context Element

In the second level document D_0 and D_1 are similar at context c_{01} and the weight is 1 because the documents are similar only at one context. The more the contexts are similar in the document sets the more the documents are contextually related, and this applies for level three (c_2), level four (c_3) and so on.

The number of levels contextual data-analysis can be performed depends on the maximum depth of the XML result set.

Figure-3.1

If document D_i and D_j are not related at the level "i" then can not qualify for "i+1" level contextual analysis.

4. ANALYSIS AND CONCERNS

Certain advantages associated with the approach are

- Similarity is user controlled, i.e. it's only measured using terms of interest to the user as shown in the Figure-4.0, each circle represents a result set, the more the circles the better relations among documents is established.

Figure-4.0

- In the above Figure-4.0 the documents that happen to occur in most of the intersections can be considered as most relevant document to the user.
- Using this approach if all the possible search criteria's are defined at First-level then the resulting document similarity metrics can be mapped to the similarity metrics of a traditional document-similarity text-analysis process. Most of the traditional document-similarity approaches are one-shot calculations, any change in the state of the data leads to massive computations, this approach is incremental.
- Traditional text-mining algorithms require taxonomies/ ontologies to leverage data-analysis with semantic equivalence but with this approach user can define such relations among keywords within the search criteria using simple algebra, so the data-analysis algorithms will be smart to identify the relations, for example in a search criteria user can define

Plasma Control Unit OR PCU

In this case the result set for the search strings will be a union of result sets for each string and the relationship will be noted and user for further data-analysis.

$$F(T_0) \text{ OR } F(T_1) = R_0 \cup R_1$$

- Similarity can be calculated removing the need to maintain result sets.

⁴ This image is a screenshot from a working prototype based on the approach.

- Cost is $O(n)$ significantly less than statistical and traditional text-mining algorithms.
- With proper algorithms the relationship weights among documents can be adjusted for dynamic data changes in the document.

The concerns associated with this approach are

- Only a few searches will not produce useful similarity metrics because calculation of similarity among documents is directly proportional to the number of search criteria definitions.
- Naïve users will pollute similarity metrics.
- The dynamic changing documents may significantly impact the process of data-analysis algorithm because all the relationship with the document will have to change.
- Need to validate method, compare algorithmically/qualitatively with other techniques.

5. CONCLUSION

The approach can be very useful for search related problems as the approach can be leveraged to work on any XML database with standard query languages like XQuery or any other query language as long as the result sets produced are well structured. A prototype is been built based on this approach using Netmark as the XML database, .NET framework to build data-analysis algorithms and AJAX (Asynchronous JavaScript XML) as a presentation layer for visualizing the weighted graph. The prototype is been tested on International Space Station (ISS) related data sets. Further developments include evaluating the approach against traditional text-mining approaches, integrate standard visualization techniques with data-analysis metrics, design an optimal algorithm to address the need for dynamic changing data.

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7. BIOGRAPHY

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